

Scalable Graphene-Induced Soft-Structured Fluids Enable Confinement-Activated Leakage Control

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Soft-structured fluids provide a strategy to control flow under extreme geometric confinement without compromising bulk processability. The incorporation of scalable graphene nanoplatelets (≈ 10 nm thick, ≈ 300 nm median lateral size) into a commercial hydraulic oil induces a weak but finite elastic contribution while preserving predominantly Newtonian steady-shear behavior. Linear viscoelastic measurements reveal a terminal-regime response characterized by viscous-dominated dissipation and a subdominant elastic component in unconfined flow. Under confinement, performance is governed by the competition between pressure-driven drainage and viscous refresh, captured by a dimensionless stress ratio. In this regime, the marginal bulk elasticity acts as a

singular perturbation of the lubrication balance. System-level tests on external gear pumps with different nominal displacements show pronounced improvements in volumetric efficiency selectively in the low-speed, high-pressure regime where leakage dominates. The efficiency gain scales linearly with the stress ratio, and the proportionality factor increases with pumped volume per revolution, indicating an extensive geometric amplification of the confinement-activated response. These results establish confinement-activated rheological design as a route to translate weak bulk viscoelasticity into macroscopic leakage control in hydraulic systems.

1. Introduction

Flows under extreme geometric confinement play a central role in a wide range of physical and technological systems, including lubrication, sealing, microfluidic transport, and hydraulic actuation. In these conditions, flow is restricted to micron-scale gaps separating moving components, where macroscopic behavior is governed by thin-film stability, drainage, and rupture rather than by bulk viscous dissipation alone. Early experiments showed that confined liquid films are highly sensitive to pressure gradients and boundary conditions, with small perturbations accelerating drainage and film failure.[1] Theoretical analyses of thin-film hydrodynamics further demonstrated that such flows are intrinsically unstable, with film thickness and load-bearing capacity determined by a delicate balance between viscous stresses, capillarity, and interfacial forces.[2] From a molecular perspective, confinement introduces additional force contributions absent in bulk flow, fundamentally altering fluid response at small separations.[3] These effects are further modified when hydrodynamic boundary conditions deviate from ideal no-slip behavior, leading to departures from classical lubrication predictions in confined geometries.[4] In positive-displacement hydraulic machines, confined-flow conditions are intrinsic rather than exceptional. At low rotational speed and high pressure, volumetric efficiency is primarily limited by leakage through clearances comparable to the thickness of the lubricating films separating moving components. Foundational analyses of hydrostatic and external gear pumps established that leakage

losses dominate system performance in this regime and cannot be eliminated indefinitely through geometric optimization alone.[5, 6] Subsequent numerical and experimental studies confirmed that pressure-driven flow through confined gaps becomes the primary loss mechanism as rotational speed decreases, rendering conventional viscosity-based optimization progressively less effective.[7, 8] Improving efficiency under low-speed, high-pressure operation therefore remains a persistent challenge.

Conventional strategies to mitigate leakage-dominated inefficiencies rely on viscosity tuning, surface engineering, or lubricant additives. While effective in reducing friction and wear under boundary lubrication conditions, approaches targeting interfacial shear stresses remain limited when performance is controlled by pressure-driven leakage through confined clearances. Much of the literature on graphene-based lubricant additives adopts a tribological perspective, focusing on friction reduction and wear mitigation through surface-mediated mechanisms.[9, 10] More recent applied studies report incremental reductions in friction coefficients under mixed or hydrodynamic lubrication without qualitative changes in lubrication regimes.[11-13] Although these works establish graphene as a tribological modifier, they do not directly address leakage control or confined-film stability.

Beyond surface tribology, soft-matter physics offers a complementary framework in which bulk fluid microstructure influences flow behavior without inducing strong non-Newtonian effects. Weak viscoelasticity can emerge in colloidal and particulate systems due to transient connectivity, even when steady-shear behavior remains essentially Newtonian.[14, 15] Such elastic responses are often considered rheologically marginal because they remain dynamically irrelevant in unconfined bulk flow and do not lead to instabilities or gelation.[16] Nevertheless, they introduce an additional degree of freedom embedded in the fluid microstructure. A growing body of work has shown that geometric confinement can dramatically amplify the functional impact of weak elastic stresses. In confined geometries, small departures from purely viscous behavior may act as singular perturbations, qualitatively altering flow organization, pressure–flow coupling, and film

stability.[17-19] These effects typically remain invisible in bulk rheological measurements but become decisive when characteristic length scales approach those of the underlying microstructure. Graphene and other layered nanomaterials provide an attractive platform to explore this interplay between bulk rheology and confinement. Dispersions of graphene platelets modify thermophysical and rheological properties without inducing strong non-Newtonian behavior, owing to their high aspect ratio and weak, transient interactions.[20, 21] Despite these advances, the implications of weak bulk viscoelasticity for engineering systems operating under extreme confinement remain largely unexplored. In particular, a direct link between soft-matter rheological states and system-level performance in leakage-dominated hydraulic machinery has not been systematically established, even though such systems operate precisely in confinement-controlled regimes.[22] In this work, we address this gap by combining bulk rheological characterization with system-level validation on external gear pumps. We show that scalable graphene platelet additives induce a soft-structured bulk fluid state that remains essentially Newtonian under unconfined conditions while acquiring a weak, thermally robust elastic component. We further demonstrate that, under extreme confinement, this marginal rheological feature becomes functionally decisive, stabilizing confined fluid films and suppressing pressure-driven leakage. By establishing that leakage-dominated performance is governed by stress competition under confinement, and that marginal bulk elasticity can be selectively activated in this regime, this work introduces a confinement-activated rheological paradigm for fluid engineering using industrially scalable graphene formulations.[23]

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 Emergence of a Soft-Structured Fluid State in Bulk

We first characterize the bulk rheological state induced by scalable graphene platelet additives in a commercial hydraulic oil, with the aim of identifying material signatures that depart from conventional Newtonian behavior while preserving flow stability and processability. Additional details on material preparation and rheological testing conditions are provided in the Supporting

Information (Sections SI-1 and SI-2). All measurements discussed in this section are performed under unconfined conditions, well outside the leakage-dominated regimes where system-level performance gains are observed. Steady-shear viscosity η is measured under linear flow conditions. Over the investigated shear-rate window, the viscosity is essentially shear-rate independent, with no signatures of shear thinning, yield stress, or shear-induced structuring. The steady-flow response is therefore consistent with Newtonian behavior (see SI-2, Figure 1b). Linear viscoelasticity is probed by small-amplitude oscillatory shear at angular frequency ω . Under a sinusoidal deformation, the stress response defines the complex shear modulus $G^*(\omega) = G'(\omega) + iG''(\omega)$, where $G'(\omega)$ represents elastic energy storage and $G''(\omega)$ viscous dissipation. For a purely Newtonian liquid, the loss modulus scales linearly with frequency, $G''(\omega) = \eta \cdot \omega$, while the storage modulus approaches zero, $G'(\omega) \rightarrow 0$, corresponding to the terminal regime of linear viscoelasticity .[24]

Figure 1. Bulk rheological characterization of the base oil (OSO) and the graphene-modified formulation (OSO+GOX). (a) Temperature dependence of viscosity. (b) Steady-shear viscosity as a

function of shear rate at different temperatures, confirming essentially Newtonian behavior for both fluids. (c) Loss modulus G'' and (d) Storage modulus G' as a function of frequency. Both fluids exhibit terminal-regime scaling ($G'' \sim \omega$ and $G' \sim \omega^2$). Dashed vertical lines indicate the crossover frequency $f_c (G' = G'')$, corresponding to a characteristic viscoelastic relaxation time $\tau_c \approx 1/\omega_c$, with $\omega_c = 2\pi f_c$.

Figure 1a shows the temperature-dependent viscosity of the base oil (OSO) and the graphene-modified formulation (OSO+GOX) over the range 40–100 °C. At ambient temperature, the two fluids exhibit comparable viscosities, indicating that graphene addition does not introduce a viscosity penalty under nominal operating conditions. Upon increasing temperature, however, the modified fluid displays reduced thermal thinning, resulting in an enhanced viscosity index. Figure 1b reports the steady-shear viscosity as a function of shear rate at different temperatures. In both formulations the viscosity remains essentially shear-rate independent over the investigated range, confirming Newtonian steady-flow behavior.

Figures 1c and 1d report the frequency dependence of the loss and storage moduli for the two formulations, respectively. In both cases the response remains strongly loss-dominated across the explored frequency range, with $G'' \gg G'$ and $G''(\omega) \approx \eta\omega$, consistent with terminal-regime liquid behavior. The moduli decrease with increasing temperature following the reduction in viscosity of the base oil. As highlighted in Figure S1 and Figure 1c-d by the dashed vertical lines, both fluids exhibit a $G'-G''$ crossover at a frequency f_c , corresponding to the angular frequency $\omega_c = 2\pi f_c$. This crossover defines an empirical viscoelastic relaxation timescale $\tau_c \approx 1/\omega_c$. The crossover frequency is slightly shifted toward higher values for the graphene-modified formulation, indicating weak elastic correlations associated with the dispersed nanoplatelets. The dependence of f_c on temperature remains modest over the explored range. Importantly, despite this shift both fluids retain a viscous-dominated response without the emergence of an elastic plateau, confirming that bulk flow remains essentially Newtonian.[15] These results identify the graphene-containing formulation as a soft-structured Newtonian fluid: viscous-dominated in bulk flow while embedding a weak elastic degree of freedom that remains dynamically silent under unconfined conditions.

Although this elastic contribution is negligible under unconfined conditions, it introduces an additional stress component that may become hydrodynamically relevant when the fluid is confined within micron-scale clearances. Under such conditions, the stability of the lubricating film is governed by the competition between pressure-driven drainage and viscous refresh. Even marginal elastic stresses may therefore perturb the confined lubrication balance, suggesting a mechanism through which weak bulk viscoelasticity can be amplified under geometric confinement.

2.2 Confinement Scaling and Stress Competition

The bulk rheology places the modified formulation in the terminal regime, where elasticity is subdominant and vanishes as $\omega \rightarrow 0$. Under unconfined conditions this weak elastic contribution does not affect macroscopic flow behavior. Extreme geometric confinement, however, alters the relevant stress balance.

When flow is restricted to micron-scale clearances, pressure gradients drive film drainage with a scale set by the pressure drop ΔP , while rotational motion refreshes the confined film at a shear rate proportional to the rotational speed n . At the level of scaling, drainage increases with ΔP , whereas viscous refresh scales with $\eta \cdot n$. The competition between these effects defines the dimensionless stress ratio $\Lambda = \Delta P / (\eta n)$, where n is expressed in s^{-1} . Because η is directly determined from the bulk linear response through $\eta \simeq G''/\omega$, the parameter Λ provides a direct bridge between the rheological state identified in Figure 1 and the hydrodynamic stresses governing confined leakage flows. In a purely Newtonian fluid, leakage-dominated behavior is governed entirely by this stress competition.

Thin confined films, however, are intrinsically sensitive to additional stress contributions. Even small elastic stresses – negligible in bulk flow – may perturb pressure–flow coupling when the gap thickness approaches characteristic structural scales of the fluid microstructure. In thin lubrication films, the volumetric leakage rate scales approximately with the cube of the film thickness. As a result, even small perturbations of the stress balance that stabilize the gap can produce disproportionately large reductions in pressure-driven leakage. Under these conditions, weak elastic

stresses associated with the platelet microstructure can oppose local gap collapse and delay drainage dynamics, effectively stabilizing the confined lubrication film. The graphene nanoplatelets used in this work have sub-micrometric lateral dimensions (median ≈ 300 nm, range ≈ 50 – 800 nm) and multilayer thickness of approximately ≈ 10 nm.[21] Although these scales remain smaller than the micron-scale clearances characteristic of external gear pumps, they are comparable to the thickness of confined lubrication films formed under load, where hydrodynamic pressure locally reduces the effective film thickness to the sub-micrometric range. Under such conditions, the nanoplatelets introduce structural correlations that can influence the stability of confined lubricating films. Weak elastic stresses may therefore be hydrodynamically amplified in thin films and modify their stability. This framework provides the physical basis for interpreting the system-level measurements presented below.

2.3 System-Level Validation under Extreme Confinement

We now turn to the functional response of the graphene-modified fluid under extreme geometric confinement, where bulk rheological measurements alone are insufficient to predict system-level behavior. Extreme geometric confinement converts marginal bulk viscoelasticity into a singular perturbation of the lubrication dynamics, stabilizing thin fluid films and suppressing pressure-driven leakage. In positive-displacement hydraulic machines such as external gear pumps, fluid flow occurs within micron-scale clearances separating moving components. Under these conditions, performance is governed primarily by the stability of thin lubricating films rather than by bulk viscous dissipation. Pressure-driven drainage and local film disruption can open leakage pathways that dominate volumetric losses, particularly at low rotational speed and high pressure.

Within this boundary-dominated regime, the weak elastic contribution identified in Section 2.1 – as dynamically irrelevant under unconfined flow – may act under confinement as a singular perturbation of the lubrication balance. Even marginal elastic stresses, negligible compared to viscous stresses in bulk rheology, can modify pressure–flow coupling and gap stability when characteristic length scales approach those of the underlying fluid microstructure. This

interpretation is consistent with theoretical and experimental studies of soft lubrication and elastohydrodynamic coupling, which demonstrate that weak compliance or elasticity can reorganize confined flow fields despite the absence of strong non-Newtonian behavior in bulk.[17, 18] More broadly, thin-film lubrication problems are known to be highly sensitive to additional stress contributions: even weak intermolecular forces or compliant responses can qualitatively alter drainage dynamics in confined geometries.[25, 26] The system-level consequences of this confinement-activated mechanism are assessed through performance tests conducted on an external gear pump with nominal displacement $2.7 \text{ cc}\cdot\text{rev}^{-1}$ operating over a wide range of rotational speeds n and pressure drops ΔP . Volumetric efficiency E_v is evaluated under steady-state conditions.

Figure 2. Confinement Scaling of Pump Performance. Volumetric efficiency E_v and relative efficiency gain ΔE_v , measured for the external gear pump with nominal displacement $2.7 \text{ cc}\cdot\text{rev}^{-1}$. (a) Volumetric efficiency E_v as a function of rotational speed n at different outlet pressures ΔP , measured for OSO and OSO+GOX. (b) Relative efficiency gain ΔE_v (percentage increase of OSO+GOX relative to OSO) plotted versus $\Lambda = \Delta P / (\eta n)$ calculated using rotational speed converted from rpm to s^{-1} . The viscosity η is evaluated at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, corresponding to the stabilized operating temperature of the hydraulic circuit during the low-speed measurements; the two formulations differ by approximately 2% in viscosity at this temperature, and a single representative value is used for the construction of Λ . Dashed line: least-squares linear fit. (c) Pressure–speed operating map showing the region where efficiency differences are observed.

Figure 2a shows the volumetric efficiency as a function of rotational speed at different pressures for both the base oil and the graphene-modified formulation. At high rotational speeds, where leakage losses are comparatively small, the two fluids exhibit nearly identical efficiencies. In contrast, pronounced differences emerge at low rotational speed and high pressure, where leakage dominates system performance. In this regime, the graphene-modified fluid consistently achieves

higher volumetric efficiency, and the enhancement increases with pressure. This selective improvement is consistent with enhanced stability of confined lubrication films rather than changes in bulk viscous dissipation. To test the confinement-scaling framework introduced in Section 2.2, the relative efficiency gain $\Delta E_v = \frac{E_{v,OSO+GOX} - E_{v,OSO}}{E_{v,OSO}}$ is evaluated from the volumetric efficiency (Section SI-3). The efficiency gain is then plotted as a function of the stress ratio $\Lambda = \Delta P / (\eta n)$ (Figure 2b). The data collapse onto a monotonic trend, indicating that leakage-dominated performance is governed primarily by the competition between pressure forcing and viscous refresh captured by Λ . This scaling confirms that the observed gains cannot be attributed to pressure or rotational speed independently, but instead reflect a confinement-controlled regime. The complete low-speed dataset supporting this behavior is reported in Section SI-4.

To assess the robustness of this scaling across device geometries, the experiments were repeated on a second external gear pump with a smaller nominal displacement of $0.8 \text{ cc}\cdot\text{rev}^{-1}$, in addition to the pump reported in Figure 2 ($2.7 \text{ cc}\cdot\text{rev}^{-1}$). When analyzed in terms of the stress ratio, the same linear dependence of ΔE_v is recovered (Section SI-5). Notably, the fitted proportionality factor increases with nominal displacement, while the ratio between the slope and nominal displacement remains approximately constant within experimental uncertainty. This behavior indicates that the confinement-activated response is not device-specific but reflects an extensive geometric contribution that scales with pumped volume per revolution. Whereas Λ captures the stress competition governing leakage, the magnitude of the efficiency gain is set by pump geometry, resulting in a displacement-dependent prefactor. The geometric interpretation of the scaling prefactor is discussed in Section SI-6.

Importantly, the efficiency enhancement cannot be rationalized solely in terms of viscosity. Bulk measurements show that the two fluids exhibit comparable viscosities under nominal operating conditions, and the moderate suppression of thermal thinning alone cannot account for the magnitude and operating-point selectivity of the observed improvements. Furthermore, the

improvement in volumetric efficiency is substantially larger than the variations observed in torque efficiency (see SI-4), which remain comparatively modest. This hierarchy of effects indicates that the dominant contribution arises from leakage suppression rather than from friction reduction or surface-mediated tribological mechanisms. The data therefore point to enhanced stability of confined lubricating films, which reduces pressure-driven drainage in micron-scale clearances. Independent tribological measurements supporting this conclusion are reported in Section SI-7. Figure 2c summarizes the operating envelope in the pressure–speed plane. The largest efficiency gains are observed in the low-speed, high-pressure region, where confinement is most severe and leakage losses are most detrimental. This regime coincides with conditions under which marginal elastic stresses are expected to exert maximal influence on confined-flow stability. Taken together, these results demonstrate that extreme geometric confinement converts a weak bulk rheological feature into a dominant functional mechanism at the system level, providing direct experimental validation of the confinement-induced amplification framework.

3. Conclusions

In this work, scalable graphene platelet additives are shown to engineer a soft-structured hydraulic fluid whose bulk rheological response remains essentially Newtonian while embedding a weak, thermally robust elastic degree of freedom. Linear viscoelastic measurements reveal a terminal-regime behavior dominated by viscous dissipation, with a subdominant elastic contribution that is dynamically negligible under unconfined flow conditions. Extreme geometric confinement alters the relevant stress balance governing fluid behavior: in leakage-dominated lubrication regimes, performance is controlled by the competition between pressure-driven drainage and viscous refresh, captured by the dimensionless stress ratio Λ .

Within this framework, the marginal bulk elasticity introduced by graphene platelets acts as a singular perturbation of the confined lubrication problem, becoming hydrodynamically amplified when flow is restricted to micron-scale clearances. System-level measurements on external gear

pumps with different nominal displacements validate this confinement-scaling picture and reveal that the proportionality factor governing efficiency gains increases with pumped volume per revolution. The graphene-modified formulation exhibits significant improvements in volumetric efficiency selectively in the low-speed, high-pressure regime where leakage dominates. The collapse of performance data as a function of Λ demonstrates that the observed enhancement does not arise from viscosity changes alone, nor from friction reduction or surface-mediated tribological effects, but from improved stability of confined fluid films. More broadly, this study establishes a confinement-activated rheological mechanism that links bulk soft-matter physics to macroscopic hydrodynamic control. The proportionality between the scaling prefactor and nominal displacement confirms the extensive character of the mechanism and demonstrates that geometric confinement provides a practical route to amplify marginal bulk viscoelasticity into macroscopic leakage control in hydraulic systems.

4. Experimental Section/Methods

Materials and fluid preparation

The reference fluid (OSO) used in this study is a commercial mineral hydraulic oil classified as ISO VG 46, commonly employed in positive-displacement hydraulic machinery. The graphene-enhanced formulation (OSO+GOX) was obtained by dispersing exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets into the same base oil. The nanoplatelets consist of multilayer graphene flakes with typical lateral dimensions in the range 100–200 nm and thickness of approximately 10 nm. Graphene platelets were added at a concentration of 0.5 wt% using a scalable dispersion protocol. The preparation procedure involved mechanical stirring followed by ultrasonication to promote homogeneous dispersion of the platelets within the oil. No surfactants, polymeric thickeners, or chemical functionalization agents were employed. The resulting formulation was filtered through a 1 μm filter to remove possible agglomerates. Visual inspection and time-dependent observations

confirmed the absence of sedimentation or phase separation over several months under ambient storage conditions.

Rheological measurements

Bulk rheological characterization was performed using a rotational rheometer (Discovery HR20, TA Instruments) equipped with a cone–plate geometry (60 mm diameter, 2° cone angle), suitable for low-viscosity fluids. Steady-shear measurements were conducted over a shear-rate range selected to remain within the linear flow regime of the fluids. Oscillatory measurements were carried out under small-amplitude strain conditions to ensure linear viscoelastic response. Temperature was controlled using a Peltier-based system integrated into the rheometer, allowing measurements over the range relevant to hydraulic operation. Each measurement was repeated multiple times to verify reproducibility and to exclude time-dependent or history-dependent effects. Detailed testing protocols, including strain amplitudes, frequency ranges, and temperature ramps, are reported in the Supporting Information, SI-2.

Gear pump test bench

System-level performance measurements were conducted on external gear pumps integrated into a closed-loop hydraulic test bench located at the Fluid Power Laboratory of the Department of Industrial, Electronic and Mechanical Engineering (DIEM), Università degli Studi Roma Tre. Two external gear pumps with different nominal displacements were investigated to assess the robustness of the observed trends across pump geometries. The hydraulic circuit allows independent control of rotational speed, outlet pressure, and operating temperature. The pumps were driven by an electric motor through a torque meter, and the circuit was equipped with pressure regulation and flow control components. All measurements were performed under steady-state conditions after thermal equilibration of the system. The same test bench, pump configuration, and operating protocol were used for both the reference fluid and the graphene-enhanced formulation. An extended description of the hydraulic test bench and pump geometry is provided in Sections SI-8 and SI-9.

Instrumentation and data acquisition

Torque was measured using a Burster 8661 torque meter equipped with an optical encoder for rotational speed acquisition. Outlet pressure was monitored using a piezoresistive pressure transducer (Kistler 4005), while flow rate was measured with a volumetric flow meter (VS 0.1, VSE Volumentech GmbH). Fluid temperature was monitored using class 1/10 DIN resistance temperature detectors (RTDs). All signals were acquired using a National Instruments PXIe-based data acquisition system. Data were recorded continuously during pump operation and averaged over stable time intervals to ensure reliable performance metrics. Instrument calibration was verified prior to the experimental campaign. Instrumentation and data acquisition details are reported in Section SI-10.

Performance metrics and repeatability

Volumetric efficiency and mechanical losses were evaluated following standard definitions commonly adopted for external gear pumps. Flow rate, pressure, torque, and rotational speed were recorded simultaneously during each test condition. The explicit definitions of efficiency metrics, along with the corresponding calculation procedures and expressions, are reported in the Supporting Information. All measurements were repeated multiple times under identical operating conditions. The observed variability remained within experimental uncertainty and did not affect the qualitative trends discussed in the main text.

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SI-1. Materials and Fluid Preparation

The reference fluid (OSO) is a commercial mineral hydraulic oil classified as ISO VG 46, widely used in industrial hydraulic systems. The graphene-enhanced formulation (OSO+GOX) was obtained by dispersing exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets into the base oil at a concentration of 0.5 wt%. The graphene additive used in this work corresponds to the commercial multilayer graphene nanoplatelets. Morphological characterization reported in previous studies,[1] shows sub-micrometric lateral dimensions with a median size of ≈ 300 nm (range ≈ 50 –800 nm) and thickness around ≈ 10 nm (range ≈ 4 –19 nm). These dimensions correspond to stacks of several graphene layers with high aspect ratio, enabling stable dispersion in lubricating oils while remaining well below the characteristic roughness of metallic contact surfaces. The dispersion protocol involved mechanical stirring followed by ultrasonication to ensure homogeneous platelet distribution. No surfactants, polymeric thickeners, or chemical functionalization agents were employed during preparation. After dispersion, the fluid was filtered through a 1 μm filter to remove possible aggregates. Long-term stability was assessed through visual inspection and time-dependent measurements, confirming the absence of sedimentation or phase separation over several months under ambient storage conditions.

SI-2. Rheological Measurement Protocols and results

Bulk rheological measurements were performed using a rotational rheometer (Discovery HR20, TA Instruments) equipped with a cone–plate geometry (60 mm diameter, 2° cone angle). Steady-shear tests were carried out over a wide shear-rate range (0.01–1000 s⁻¹) to verify linear flow behavior and exclude shear-induced structuring or non-Newtonian effects. Both fluids exhibit a Newtonian plateau around 10 s⁻¹, which was therefore selected as the reference shear rate for temperature-dependent viscosity measurements. The viscosity–temperature dependence was measured at a constant shear rate of 10 s⁻¹ while temperature was increased from 40 °C to 100 °C at a controlled rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. This dataset provides the basis for evaluating the thermal stability of the lubricant.

Oscillatory rheology measurements were conducted under small-amplitude strain conditions to ensure linear viscoelastic response. Strain-amplitude sweeps were performed to identify the linear viscoelastic region, and a strain amplitude of 15% was selected for all frequency sweeps. Frequency sweeps were performed over the accessible frequency range (0.01–100 Hz) using this constant strain amplitude. Measurements were carried out at controlled temperatures of 40 °C, 70 °C, and 100 °C using a Peltier-based temperature control system integrated into the rheometer. Each experiment was repeated multiple times to ensure reproducibility and to exclude time-dependent or history-dependent effects.

The steady-shear viscosity of OSO and OSO+GOX remains essentially independent of shear rate over the investigated range (0.1–1000 s⁻¹) at all temperatures, confirming Newtonian flow behavior for both formulations (Figure 1a). The graphene-modified formulation exhibits a slightly higher viscosity compared to the base oil, consistent with weak hydrodynamic interactions introduced by dispersed nanoplatelets. Importantly, no measurable shear thinning or thickening is observed, indicating that graphene addition does not induce shear-dependent microstructural organization in the bulk fluid. As expected, viscosity decreases with increasing temperature for both systems, reflecting the thermally activated reduction of base-oil viscosity. Overall, the graphene-modified formulation preserves the Newtonian steady-flow character of the base lubricant.

Figure S1. Frequency sweep measurements for the base oil (OSO) and the graphene-modified formulation (OSO+GOX) at three temperatures (40, 70, and 100 °C).

Storage modulus G' (triangles) and loss modulus G'' (circles) are reported as a function of oscillation frequency. The response remains viscous-dominated across the explored frequency range, with $G'' > G'$ at low frequencies and a crossover between the two moduli occurring at higher frequencies. The crossover frequency f_c , defined by $G' = G''$, is used to estimate the characteristic relaxation time $\tau_c \approx 1/\omega_c$ with $\omega_c = 2\pi f_c$. These measurements provide the complete oscillatory rheology dataset corresponding to the summary representation reported in Figure 1 of the main text.

Oscillatory rheology discussion

Oscillatory rheology measurements (Figure S1) show that both OSO and OSO+GOX remain strongly loss-dominated across the accessible frequency range, with G'' exceeding G' by more than one order of magnitude at low frequency, consistent with terminal fluid behavior. Both formulations exhibit a $G'-G''$ crossover defining an empirical viscoelastic timescale $\tau_c \sim 1/\omega_c$ that separates the long-time viscous regime from the shorter-time regime where elastic storage becomes measurable. Increasing temperature systematically shifts the crossover toward lower frequencies (OSO: ~ 50 Hz at 40 °C to ~ 5 Hz at 100 °C; OSO+GOX: ~ 63 Hz to ~ 12 Hz), consistent with the thermally induced reduction of viscous dissipation ($G'' \approx \eta\omega$). Importantly, the graphene-modified formulation follows the same thermal trend while remaining slightly shifted toward higher crossover frequencies, indicating weak elastic correlations introduced by the dispersed nanoplatelets.

The absence of any low-frequency elastic plateau and the comparable magnitude of the moduli for OSO and OSO+GOX confirm that both fluids retain a liquid-like response across experimentally relevant timescales. Comparable rheological responses have been reported for graphene-based dispersions, where high-aspect-ratio nanoplatelets introduce weak elastic contributions while preserving essentially Newtonian bulk flow behavior.[2, 3]

SI-3. Definitions of Performance Metrics and Calculation Procedures

Pump performance is quantified in terms of power conversion efficiency and its decomposition into volumetric and torque contributions, following standard definitions for external gear pumps. The overall pump efficiency, E_{pump} , is defined as the ratio between the hydraulic power P_{hyd} delivered to the hydraulic circuit and the mechanical power P_{mech} supplied at the pump shaft:

$$E_{pump} = \frac{P_{hyd}}{P_{mech}} \quad (SI3.1)$$

The hydraulic power is given by the product of the delivered flow rate Q and the load pressure ΔP , while the mechanical power supplied to the pump shaft is obtained from the measured torque C and rotational speed n . Using these experimentally accessible quantities, the overall pump efficiency can be expressed as:

$$E_{pump} = \frac{Q \Delta P}{2\pi n C} \quad (SI3.2)$$

It is convenient to decompose the overall efficiency into a volumetric contribution, accounting for leakage losses, and a torque (or hydro-mechanical) contribution, accounting for mechanical and viscous losses. Accordingly, the overall efficiency can be written as the product of the volumetric efficiency E_v and the torque efficiency E_t :

$$E_{pump} = \frac{Q}{V_{disp} \cdot n} \cdot \frac{V_{disp} \cdot \Delta P}{C} = E_v \cdot E_t \quad (SI3.3)$$

Here, V_{disp} denotes the actual pump displacement. The torque efficiency E_t is defined as the ratio between the theoretical torque C_{th} , required to generate the pressure increase ΔP and the experimentally measured torque C :

$$E_t = \frac{C_{th}}{C} = \frac{V_{disp} \cdot \Delta P}{C} \quad (SI3.4)$$

The actual displacement V_{disp} of the pump is determined experimentally from measurements performed under zero-load conditions, where volumetric losses due to leakage and fluid compressibility are negligible. Using the measured flow rate Q_0 and rotational speed n_0 under these conditions, the displacement is calculated as:

$$V_{disp} = \frac{Q_0}{n_0} \quad (SI3.5)$$

Finally, the volumetric efficiency E_v is obtained as the ratio between the measured flow rate Q and the theoretical flow rate Q_{th} , defined as the product of the actual displacement and the rotational speed:

$$E_v = \frac{Q}{Q_{th}} \quad (SI3.6)$$

All performance metrics reported in the main text are computed using these definitions, applied consistently to both the reference and graphene-enhanced formulations.

SI-4. Supplementary Pump Performance Results at Very Low Speed

This section reports the complete experimental dataset supporting the pump performance analysis discussed in Section 2.2 of the main manuscript. The tables summarize the full percentage differences in volumetric and torque efficiency between OSO and OSO+GOX, while the performance maps provide a graphical representation of efficiency trends as a function of pressure and rotational speed. These supplementary results document the operating-point dependence of the observed efficiency gains under low-speed, high-pressure conditions, where confinement-induced leakage dominates system performance.

Table S1. % Differences on volumetric efficiency, pump 1

Shaft speed (rpm)	Pressure (bar)	Volumetric efficiency (E_v)		% difference (ΔE_v)
		OSO	OSO+GOX	
350 rpm	180	0.68	0.76	+11.8
	150	0.73	0.79	+8.2
	60	0.87	0.9	+3.4
250 rpm	180	0.51	0.69	+35.3
	150	0.6	0.72	+20.0
	60	0.81	0.85	+4.9
150 rpm	180	0.17	0.31	+82.4
	150	0.51	0.63	+23.5
	60	0.65	0.75	+15.4

Table S2. % Differences on torque efficiency, pump 1

Shaft speed (rpm)	Pressure (bar)	Torque efficiency (E_t)		% difference (ΔE_t)
		OSO	OSO+GOX	
350 rpm	170	0.81	0.86	+6.2
	130	0.85	0.88	+3.5
	60	0.83	0.84	+1.2
250 rpm	170	0.72	0.83	+15.3
	130	0.82	0.87	+6.1
	60	0.82	0.83	+1.2
150 rpm	170	0.64	0.72	+12.5
	130	0.72	0.83	+15.3
	60	0.78	0.81	+3.8

Table S3. % Differences on volumetric efficiency, pump 2

Shaft speed (rpm)	Pressure (bar)	Volumetric efficiency (E_v)		% difference (ΔE_v)
		OSO	OSO+GOX	
350 rpm	170	0.78	0.83	+6.4
	130	0.83	0.86	+3.6
	60	0.91	0.92	+1.1
250 rpm	170	0.71	0.77	+8.5
	130	0.77	0.81	+5.2
	60	0.87	0.90	+3.4
150 rpm	170	0.52	0.62	+19.2
	130	0.62	0.69	+11.3
	60	0.80	0.84	+5.0

Table S4. % Differences on torque efficiency, pump 2

Shaft speed (rpm)	Pressure (bar)	Torque efficiency (E_t)		% difference (ΔE_t)
		OSO	OSO+GOX	
350 rpm	170	0.88	0.88	0.0
	130	0.88	0.87	-1.1
	60	0.84	0.83	-1.2
250 rpm	170	0.85	0.88	+3.4
	130	0.87	0.88	+1.1
	60	0.86	0.84	-2.4
150 rpm	170	0.77	0.85	+9.4
	130	0.85	0.87	+2.3
	60	0.81	0.84	+3.6

Figure S2. Performance maps of Pump 1 (350, 250, 150 rpm)

Figure S3. Performance maps of Pump 2 (350, 250, 150 rpm)

SI-5. Confinement Scaling for the Smaller-Displacement Device

Figure S4. Confinement Scaling in a Smaller-Displacement Device. Volumetric efficiency E_v and relative efficiency gain ΔE_v measured for the external gear pump with $V_{nom} = 0.8$ cc/rev. (a) Volumetric efficiency as a function of rotational speed at different outlet pressures for the reference and graphene-modified fluids. (b) Relative efficiency gain plotted as a function of the stress ratio $\Lambda = \Delta P / (\eta n)$, with η evaluated at 40 °C. The dashed line represents a least-squares linear fit. (c) Pressure–speed operating map highlighting the regime where efficiency differences emerge.

Table S5. Linear Scaling Parameters of the Efficiency Gain

V_{nom} (cc/rev)	Linear Regression Slope m	m / V_{nom} (cc ⁻¹ rev)
2.7	0.05±0.01	(0.05±0.01)/2.7=0.017±0.004
0.8	0.016±0.001	(0.016±0.001)/0.8=0.020±0.001

The efficiency gain follows the linear relation $\Delta E_v = m \Lambda$. Across the two devices, the fitted proportionality factor m increases with nominal displacement, while the ratio m/V_{nom} remains approximately constant within experimental uncertainty (Table S5). This behavior supports an extensive geometric scaling in which the confinement-activated response grows proportionally with pumped volume per revolution and motivates the minimal formalization presented in the following section.

SI-6. Geometric Scaling of the Proportionality Factor

The empirical results reported in Section SI-5 show that the slope m of the linear relation between efficiency gain and stress ratio depends systematically on nominal displacement V_{nom} . This section provides a compact interpretation of that trend.

The confinement scaling observed experimentally can be written as

$$\Delta E_v = m \Lambda \quad (\text{S6.1})$$

where $\Lambda = \Delta P / (\eta n)$ captures the stress competition governing leakage-dominated operation.

Across the two investigated devices, the fitted proportionality factor increases with nominal displacement, while the ratio m/V_{nom} remains approximately constant. This observation suggests that, to first approximation,

$$m = \alpha V_{nom} \quad (\text{S6.2})$$

where α is a geometry-independent constant within a given pump architecture.

Substituting yields

$$\Delta E_v = \alpha V_{nom} \Lambda \quad (\text{S6.3})$$

This scaling indicates that the confinement-activated contribution to leakage suppression is extensive with respect to pumped volume per revolution. While Λ captures the local stress balance in confined films, the absolute magnitude of the efficiency gain reflects the global volumetric throughput of the device. The proportionality between m and V_{nom} therefore provides an internal consistency check for the confinement-activation framework.

It is important to note that the stress ratio is constructed from bulk rheological quantities measured under unconfined conditions. The maximum shear rates accessible in the rheometer ($\approx 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$) remain below the effective shear rates expected in micron-scale pump clearances under operating pressures and speeds. The confinement-activated regime therefore cannot be directly reproduced in bulk rheometry. Instead, the bulk measurements identify a marginal elastic degree of freedom that becomes hydrodynamically amplified only under geometric restriction. The observed geometric scaling supports this interpretation and confirms that the efficiency enhancement arises from confinement-mediated stress reorganization rather than from bulk non-Newtonian behavior.

SI-7. Tribological Characterization: Coefficient of Friction Measurements

Tribological measurements were performed to evaluate the Coefficient Of Friction (COF) of the reference and graphene-enhanced formulations. COF was measured as a function of sliding speed at temperatures of 40 °C, 70 °C, and 100 °C under identical test conditions for both fluids.

Both formulations exhibit Stribeck-like behavior, characterized by a decrease in COF at low sliding speeds followed by a quasi-plateau at higher speeds. The graphene-enhanced fluid shows a modest but reproducible reduction in COF, particularly at elevated temperatures. No qualitative changes in lubrication regime are observed.

These measurements are reported here for completeness, as they confirm that graphene addition does not disrupt the lubrication mechanism of the base oil.

Figure S5. Coefficient of friction (COF) as a function of sliding speed for the OSO and the OSO+GOX measured at 40, 70, and 100 °C.

SI-8. Hydraulic Test Bench: Extended Description

SI-8.1 Test Bench Overview

System-level measurements were conducted at the Fluid Power Laboratory of the Department of Industrial, Electronic and Mechanical Engineering (DIIEM), Università degli Studi Roma Tre. The experimental setup consists of a closed-loop hydraulic circuit designed to test external gear pumps under controlled operating conditions.

Figure S6. (a) Front view of pump test bed at Fluid Power Laboratory of DIIEM – Roma Tre; (b) rear view of torque-meter and external gear pump assembly, right.

SI-8.2 Hydraulic Circuit Layout

A schematic representation of the hydraulic circuit is shown below. The circuit allows independent control of rotational speed, outlet pressure, and fluid temperature, enabling steady-state measurements across a wide operating envelope.

Figure S7. Schematic of the closed-loop hydraulic circuit used for pump testing.

SI-9. External Gear Pumps: Geometry and Specifications

Two external gear pumps with different nominal displacements were investigated. The pumps were selected to assess the robustness of the observed performance trends across different geometries.

Figure S8. Photographs of the two external gear pumps investigated in this study.

Table S6. Main characteristics of the external gear pumps.

Parameter	Pump 1	Pump 2
Nominal displacement (V_{nom})	2.7 cc·rev ⁻¹	0.8 cc·rev ⁻¹
Maximum pressure	190 bar	190 bar
Nominal speed range	600 – 4500 rpm	600 – 4000 rpm

SI-10. Instrumentation and Data Acquisition System

The hydraulic test bench was equipped with the following instrumentation:

Table S7: Instrumentation and DAQ system

	Component	Specification
eDRV	Electric drive	4-pole asynchronous motor and frequency converter
TM	Torque meter and optical encoder	Burster 8661
PT	Pressure transducer	Kistler 4005 piezo-resistive transducer
FM	Flow meter	VS 0.1 - VSE Volumentechnik GmbH
TT	Temperature transducer	Class 1/10 DIN RTD
DAQ System	IO module	National Instruments PXIe 6143

Table S8. Instrumentation and data acquisition system.

Component	Model	Manufacturer
Torque meter	8661	Burster
Pressure transducer	4005	Kistler
Flow meter	VS 0.1	VSE Volumentechnik GmbH
Temperature sensor	RTD Class 1/10 DIN	—
Data acquisition	PXIe 6143	National Instruments

All signals were continuously recorded during pump operation and averaged over stable measurement intervals.

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